

EXTENT OF MATHEMATICS LEARNING OUTCOMES AND COMPETENCIES ACHIEVED BY THE JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The study determined the extent of Mathematics learning outcomes achieved by the Junior High Schoolers of St. Paul University Surigao. The main instruments used to solicit information were researcher-made questionnaires. The participants of this study were 6 Mathematics teachers and 151 students at St. Paul University Surigao Junior High School during the school year 2019-2020. Data gathered were analyzed using the means, standard deviation, and t-test.

The teachers perceived that the students achieved the mathematics learning outcomes to some extent. Similarly, the students also perceived that they achieved mathematics learning outcomes to some extent. Hence, the teachers' understanding matched with students' actual achievements validating the teachers' teaching approaches. It was also revealed that there is no significant difference between the respondents' perceptions on the extent of the mathematics learning outcomes achieved by the students but there is a significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on indicators exhibit honesty and exhibit a sense of truthfulness under the CONS category.

Keywords: Mathematics Competencies, Outcome-Based Mathematics Education, Mathematics Teaching in OBE, Student Achievement.

INTRODUCTION

The present modernized society requires everyone to acquire and embody the so-called 21st-century skills and capacity where critical thinking and decision-making skills are premium to achieve sustainable development of human life, inevitable technological advancement and unavoidable total development and upgrades. Thus, the modern world problems require modern world, upright, and innovative solutions. One best way is by teaching the value of critical thinking for good decision making, spirituality, and morality for upright selection of life choices, problem-solving, and risk-taking to the minds and hearts of the growing people, our new generation learners. This is through teaching and inculcating the value of critical thinking for good decision making, risk-taking to the minds and hearts of the growing people, our new generation learners through the unique or distinct Mathematical discipline teaching.

Mathematics has been considered as one of the toughest subjects due to its complex topics and sub-disciplines which require higher critical, mental, and strategic capabilities. Thus, people consider that if one person is good in the mathematics discipline, then that person is logically and critically intelligent or advanced.

Mastrangeli (2019) believes that mathematical expertise demands effective thinking and learning methods, and these techniques transfer well to other domains not only to the cognitive and psychomotor domains but also to the affective domain of the teaching-learning process where the real values that should be embodied alongside the person's spirituality and morality are supposedly achieved. Mathematical reasoning and thinking processes generally impact knowledge acquisition and problem-solving.

Examining mathematics teaching in the classroom described by Paulinian students' success in achieving the intended learning outcomes and competencies is very beneficial and significant to Mathematics teachers in schools as this will surely equip not only the mathematics teachers but also all teachers in their respective fields of specializations in this era of non-stop curriculum advancement. Moreover, the modern world mathematics requires not only simple know-how about the subject concepts but also more on the mastery and deeper understanding of the subject leading to learners contextualizing ideas relevant of values and holistic development, applying concepts to real-life situations, realizing and self-evaluating realistic mathematical knowledge absorbed, and creation of actual existence of Mathematical concepts in the contemporary world full of life-changing and affecting scenarios requiring each learner to transform or become critical thinkers and problem solvers.

The Outcome-based education or commonly called OBE bases each part of an educational system around goals or politically termed as 'outcomes'. By the end of the educational experience, each student should have achieved the outcomes intended. There is no single specified style of teaching or assessment in OBE, instead, classes, opportunities, and assessments should all help students achieve the specified outcomes.

Furthermore, the role of the teacher adapts into an instructor, trainer, facilitator, and/or mentor based on the outcomes targeted (Spady, 2014). This study examined the extent of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by students.

Moreover, this study also explained the teachers' mathematical knowledge which might be significantly related to students' intended outcomes achievement gains and that in the end, the findings will provide support for a policy or intervening initiatives designed to improve students' mathematics achievement by improving teachers' mathematical knowledge. Lastly, this academic output may be able to present ideas to suggest how, when teaching our subject, the mathematics community might pass on our core strength: our thinking and learning methodology, which is the main ingredient in the efficient teaching of mathematics in the modern world, outcomes-based.

Framework

The study determined the extent of Mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the Junior High School students at St. Paul University Surigao. This was done after looking into the students' mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achievements in relation to the SPCEM Basic Education Graduate Outcomes and the Kto12 Mathematics Education Twin

Competency Goals. Such learning out- comes and competencies were derived from the Paulinian Core Values alongside the K to 12 Mathematics Education Framework of the Department of Education. Additionally, the concept of integrating affective domain-based instruction as an ingredient to Outcomes-based teaching to the 21st-century mathematics in the modern world learners for more meaningful and experiential learning achievements is also considered to be tack- led.

Learning Outcome. This refers to a clear statement of what a learner is expected to do, know about, and value at the end of studying which are measurable. It states both the substance of learning and how its attainment is to be demonstrated. For the Paulinian community, it refers to the SPCEM life performance behaviors intended for all Paulinian learners to achieve as a result of taking up Paulinian education. These out comes were based on the congregation's core values (SPCEM, 2018).

Learning Competency. These refer to the established set of intended skills, behaviors, and knowledge the learners are expected to master (DepEd, 2016).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the study. As shown, the DepEd Kto12 Mathematics Education Twin Competency Goals are alongside and interconnect- ed with the SPCEM Basic Education Graduate Outcomes which depicts that the study intended to join these two major variables to look into the students' achievements in relation to these joined outcomes and competencies which may describe the teaching practices and efficiency of the junior high school mathematics teachers.

To support the indicated variables for a clearer and better understanding of the concept and context of this study, the following conceptual frameworks are herein discussed and elaborated:

Figure 2. The Conceptual Framework of Mathematics Education in the Philippines

(Source: http://depedbohol.org/v2/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Math-CG_with-tagged-math-equipment.pdf)

Figure 2 shows the Conceptual Framework of Mathematics Education in the Philippines. The two goals of mathematics in the basic education levels, K-10, are Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving. Critical thinking, according to Scriven and Paul (1987) is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action.

On the other hand, according to Polya (1945 & 1962), mathematical problem solving is finding a way around a difficulty, around an obstacle, and finding a solution to a problem that is unknown. These two goals are to be achieved with organized and rigorous curriculum content, a well-defined set of high-level skills and processes, desirable values and attitudes, and appropriate tools, taking into account the different contexts of Filipino learners.

The framework is supported by the following underlying learning principles and theories interjected to be the mathematics teachers' foundation for instruction, in crafting strategies for delivery: Experiential and Situated Learning, Reflective Learning, Constructivism, Cooperative Learning and Discovery, and Inquiry-based Learning. The mathematics curriculum is grounded in these theories. Experiential Learning as advocated by David Kolb is learning that occurs by making sense of direct everyday experiences.

Experiential Learning theory defines learning as "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming experience" (Kolb, 1984). Situated Learning, theorized by Lave and Wenger, is learning in the same context in which concepts and theories are applied. Reflective Learning refers to learning that is facilitated by reflective thinking. It is not enough that learners encounter real-life situations. Deeper learning occurs when learners can think about their experiences and process these, allowing them the opportunity to make sense of and derive meaning from their experiences.

Constructivism is the theory that argues that knowledge is constructed when the learner can draw ideas from his/her own experiences and connect them to new ideas. Cooperative Learning puts a premium on active learning achieved by working with fellow learners as they all engage in a

shared task. The mathematics curriculum allows students to learn by asking relevant questions and discovering new ideas. Discovery Learning and Inquiry-based Learning (Bruner, 1961) support the idea that students learn when they make use of personal experiences to discover facts, relationships, and concepts (http://depedbohol.org/v2/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Math-CG_with-tagged-math-equipment.pdf).

Figure 3. SPC Education Ministry Basic Education Level Outcome-based Education Framework (Source: The SPC Education Ministry Educators' Congress 2018)

Sisters of Paul of Chartres Education Ministry (2018) underscores that the process of formation of the whole person is the process of imitating Jesus Christ our model—to become whole, to be truly human, to Glorify God. Furthermore, the formation of the whole person begins with the imitation of Jesus Christ our model and ends with the transformation of the person contributing to the transformation of the world, and so the ministry features in the Paulinian Formation Program the attributes of a Paulinian formator each in consonance with Paulinian Graduate Outcomes – “A Paulinian Formator is a DISCIPLE OF JESUS CHRIST, who strives for EXCELLENCE AND HOLINESS from which will flow a life of SERVANT LEADERSHIP, MUTUAL COMMUNITY RELATIONSHIP, and COMPASSIONATE STEWARDSHIP, to uplift the human and spiritual condition of the students, for the good of the Church and the society.”

Figure 3 shows the SPC education ministry's Basic education level outcome-based education framework with the Paulinian core values. Figure 4 explains that the aim of the SPC Education Ministry for its Basic Education learners is to let them achieve the intended learning outcomes aligned to the Congregation's core values – “producing young Paulinian citizens who embody the values of: CHRIST-CENTEREDNESS, the value where one devotes all endeavors, actions, and life learnings with Jesus Christ in the center of the heart exhibited through the CONSCIOUSness of the heart, mind, and the spirit thus becoming MINDFUL, SELF-DIRECTED LEARNERS & ROLE MODELS; CHARISM, the value in which a person is endowed with spiritual talents and giftedness by the Holy Spirit exhibited by being CREATIVE thus becoming CREATIVE, RESOURCEFUL EXPLORER & PROBLEM SOLVER; COMMUNITY, the value in which a person, through the Pauline spiritual teachings and discipleship, acknowledges and embodies the essence of having harmonious communal relationships with one another exhibited by being COLLABORATIVE with fellow members of the community thus becoming CREDIBLE, RESPONSIVE COMMUNICATORS, & TEAM PLAYERS; COMMISSION, the value in which one becomes a an excellent committed steward and advocate having the need to fulfill the mission of the Church exhibited by being a COMPETENT individual thus becoming CONSCIENTIOUS, ADEPT PERFORMERS & ACHIEVERS; CHARITY, the value in which one lives a life of care, kindness, generosity, and love for the others especially those who are underprivileged by being COMPASSIONATE to one another thus becoming COMMITTED ADVOCATES FOR PEACE AND UNIVERSAL WELL-BEING.”

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the extent of Mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the Junior High School students at St. Paul University Surigao. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. To what extent have the mathematics learning outcomes and competencies been achieved by the students as perceived by the respondents?
2. What is the significant difference between the participant's perceptions on the students' achieved mathematics learning outcomes and competencies?
3. Based on the findings, what recommendations can be given?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher used a quantitative research design employing a descriptive research survey approach which allowed the researcher to gather more precise and quantifiable information needed to quantify responses that may lead to expected research outcomes with the help of the identified appropriate indicators. Surendran (2019) believes that Quantitative research design is a systematic investigation of phenomena through gathering quantifiable data and performing statistical computational techniques.

The said design was also employed to determine the extent of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves. Moreover, the design also helped the researcher determine the significant difference between the participants' perceptions on the extent of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study.

Participants

The participants of this study were the Junior High School Mathematics teachers and students at St. Paul University Surigao School Year 2019-2020.

Purposive sampling technique was used in this study. Crossman (2019) defines purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling as a non-probability sampling technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of participants which decisions concerning the individuals to be included in the sample are taken by the researcher. And so, purposive because the researcher considered conducting the study only to the 6 Junior High school Mathematics teachers and 151 Science Class students who taught and enrolled respectively in St. Paul University Surigao during the school year 2019-2020. Only the science class students were considered in this study since they all had taken both regular and elective mathematics subjects offered by the university.

Data Collecting Instruments

The main instruments used to solicit information were researcher-made questionnaires. Separate sets of questionnaires for the mathematics teachers and the Junior High School students respectively were used. Moreover, the mathematics teachers and the students' questionnaires both contained items or indicators that asked primarily for their perceptions on the mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study.

Data Gathering

The researcher used questionnaires and those were personally administered to the participants of the study. Before the actual gathering of data, a letter was sent to the Principal of the Basic Education Department of the University asking for the approval to conduct the study to the mathematics teachers and science class students in the Junior High School. After the approval, the researcher administered the researcher-made questionnaires to the actual participants. The data were tallied, treated, and interpreted for analysis and discussion.

Ethical Consideration

In this study, the researcher strictly observed research ethics wherein confidentiality, privacy rights, and safety of the participants as well as the ethical practices of the researcher were strongly observed. Primarily, the researcher adhered to certain provisions applicable under the DPA Act of 2012 to protect the participants and the researcher of the study. The questionnaires of the study integrated Data Privacy consent and waivers for the sake of the security assurance for both

researcher and the participants. The researcher also respected the involved persons' feelings and opinions.

Informed-consent – the researcher ensured that individuals voluntarily participated in the research with full knowledge of relevant risks and benefits.

Maintenance of Privacy. The researcher in this study respected the feelings and personal information property rights of the informants. Hence, the confidentiality of information was ensured.

Data Analysis

In fulfilling the desire of having most reliable and appropriate results and findings on determining the characteristics of outcomes-based Mathematics teaching in St. Paul University Surigao Junior

High School, the researcher used the following statistical tools to analyze the data:

Means and Standard Deviation. These tools were used to quantify the participants' responses to the mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achievement perceptions indicators.

The following is a 4-point frequency and extensiveness Likert scale that was used as the basis for the interpretation of data yielded from the responses of the participants of the study in relation to problems 4 and 5:

Scale	Range	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
3	2.50 – 3.24	Sometimes	To Some Extent
2	1.75 – 2.49	Rarely	To Little Extent
1	1.00 – 1.74	Never	To No Extent At All

Upon statistical treatment, the interpreted data was discussed to infer and elicit proper conclusions and supporting ideas that suited to answer problems number 4 and 5 specifically on the extent of achievement of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies of the students under study as perceived by all the participants. Participants responded to each indicator in the questionnaires based on their best and honest evaluation signifying their perceptions on the achievement of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies of the students under study. Average responses within 1.00 – 1.74 were described as never frequent and meant as to no extent at all; 1.75 – 2.49 as rarely frequent and meant as to little extent; 2.50 – 3.24 as sometimes frequent and meant as to some extent; and 3.25 – 4.00 as always frequent and meant as to very much extent.

t-test. This tool was used to determine the significant difference between the participants' perceptions on the students' extent of the mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved. The difference between the participants' perceptions is considered significant if $p < 0.05$, otherwise, the null hypothesis is accepted stating that there is no significant difference between the participants' perceptions.

Findings, Results, and Discussion

On the Extent of Mathematics Learning Outcomes and Competencies Achieved by the Students as Perceived by the Respondents

Table 1 shows the CONS mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves. For teachers, CONS was achieved by the students to very much extent given the average Mean=3.33 and average SD=0.516 which means that the teachers perceived that the students are Conscious, mindful self-directed learners & role models embodying Christ-centeredness to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. For students, CONS was achieved by the students only to some extent given the average Mean=2.87 and average SD=0.636 which means that the students themselves perceived that they are Conscious, mindful self-directed learners & role models embodying Christ-centeredness to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Christ-centeredness is the value where one devotes all endeavors, actions, and life learnings with Jesus Christ in the center of the heart exhibited by being Conscious in heart, mind, and the spirit thus becoming mindful, self-directed learner & role model. Paulinians who are Christ-centered are bound to exhibit and act morally with faithfulness and they demonstrate actions that show that they are learning independently and acting actively as a role model in loving and following Jesus Christ, who, at all times speak good words and guards oneself against wrongdoings and bad or evil things and he or she manifests honesty and truthfulness in his or her relationships and is ethical and moral in his or her transactions (SPCEM, 2018).

Furthermore, according to SPC Education Ministry (2018), a Christ-centered, Conscious, mindful self-directed learner & role model must demonstrate actions that show respect for oneself by being decent and modest in his or her dressing, manners, and speech both in public and private places. Hence, there is respect for everyone regard- less of faith, culture, and differences. Moreover, being a self-directed person, a Paulinian manages his or her time and energy to allow for regular periods of quiet and re- flection, prayer, renewal, and direction setting and that he or she, being a conscious role model speaks good words and guards oneself against wrongdoings and bad or evil things. He or she manifests honesty and truthfulness in his or her relationships and is ethical and moral in his or her transactions. All these desired actions and behaviors would mean exhibiting a sense of dignity which is intended to be present in the learning tasks and assessments. It may be contextualized or stimulated by the learners upon doing learning tasks and assessments.

Table 1. The CONS mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by the participants

Indicators	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	p-value
1. exhibit religious faith sense as students fulfill and relate tasks to real-life situations.	3.0	0.63	TSE	2.8	0.809	TSE	0.678
	0	2		6			
2. exhibit religious morality as students fulfill and relate tasks to real-life situations.	3.3	0.51	TVME	2.8	0.781	TSE	0.105
	3	6		1			
3. exhibit life discipleship	3.0	0.63	TSE	2.8	0.792	TSE	0.672
	0	2		6			
4. exhibit honesty.	3.6	0.51	TVME	2.8	0.718	TSE	0.004
	7	6		1			
5. exhibit sense of truthfulness	3.6	0.51	TVME	2.9	0.724	TSE	0.018
	7	6		5			
6. exhibit reliability.	3.1	0.75	TSE	2.9	0.693	TSE	0.535
	7	3		9			
7. exhibit integrity in doing the learning activities and assessments	3.3	0.51	TVME	3.0	0.744	TSE	0.309
	3	6		2			
8. value dignity in doing the learning activities and assessments	3.3	0.51	TVME	3.0	0.801	TSE	0.431
	3	6		7			
9. show sensibility or mindfulness leading students to proactively respond to the challenges of the changing times.	3.1	0.40	TSE	2.9	0.794	TSE	0.515
	7	8		5			
10. demonstrate the traits of a role model as students accomplish their tasks.	3.1	0.75	TSE	2.7	0.800	TSE	0.158
	7	3		0			
11. demonstrate the traits of a self-directed person as students accomplish their tasks.	2.8	0.75	TSE	2.8	0.753	TSE	0.863
	3	3		9			
12. demonstrate the traits of an upright person as students accomplish their tasks.	3.3	0.51	TVME	2.9	0.731	TSE	0.180
	3	6		3			

13. exhibit good decision-making capabilities considering religious motivation and uprightness as the core of the human heart and mind.	3.0 0	0.63 2	TSE	2.8 4	0.767	TSE	0.617
14. easily find solutions when solving problems.	2.8 3	0.40 8	TSE	2.5 4	0.885	TSE	0.426
15. easily identify possible causes and consequences of certain actions when solving problems.	2.8 3	0.40 8	TSE	2.7 4	0.812	TSE	0.784
16. take risks in finding solutions to problems and answer such problems in given time duration.	2.6 7	0.51 6	TSE	2.8 0	0.841	TSE	0.698
Average	3.3 3	0.51 6	TVME	2.8 7	0.636	TSE	0.083

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

CONS=Conscious, Mindful Self-Directed Learners & Role Models / Christ-centeredness Core Value Independent
sample-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale:	Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
	3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
	1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
	1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Looking closely at the highest results in Table 1, it can be inferred that for teachers, both indicators 4. Exhibit honesty (Mean=3.67; SD=0.516, verbally interpreted to very much extent) and 5. Exhibit a sense of truthfulness (Mean=3.67; SD=0.516, verbally interpreted to very much extent) got the highest mean ratings. This implies that for the teachers, the students exhibit honesty and a sense of truthfulness to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. However, the results under the students' column showed differently. For students, indicator 8. Value dignity in doing the learning activities and assessments (Mean=3.07; SD=0.801, verbally interpreted to some extent) got the highest mean rating. This implies that the students themselves value dignity in doing the learning activities and assessments to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

The Department of Education (2016) emphasized that honesty, accuracy, and reliability are some of the major values and positive attitude traits a young Filipino must demonstrate as they encounter mathematical knowledge and skills learning inside and outside of the classroom setting. These values, when consistently integrated with the mathematics class and knowledge engagements as strongly promoted by the teachers' approaches and strategies, surely yield a meaningful and valuable learning experience for Filipino learners that will last longer than the mathematical content knowledge itself. Moreover, it was understood by the researcher that valuing dignity which also pertains to self-respect, esteem, pride, and self-worth, is one of the components of becoming a self-directed and role model person, hence included as an indicator of the CONS outcome and competency that is being assessed from the learners.

Brown (2010) highlighted that the learning activities and assessments by principle should always be inclusive, equitable, and should be an integral part of program design and should directly relate to the content or curriculum aims and learning outcomes. Being inclusive and equitable, assessment should ensure that tasks and procedures do not disadvantage any group or individual. Moreover, such assessment tasks should primarily reflect the nature of the subject but should also ensure that students have the opportunity to develop a range of skills, capabilities, and values, including all in the affective domain that promotes self-worth, esteem, dignity, and even entire personality development.

On the other hand, looking closely at the lowest results shown by Table 1, it can be inferred that for teachers, indicator number 16. Take risks in finding solutions to problems and answer such

problems in a given time duration got the lowest mean rating of 2.67, $SD=0.516$, and verbally interpreted to some extent. This implies that the mathematics teachers perceived that the students under study take risks in finding solutions to problems and answer such problems in given time duration to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

For the students, indicator number 14. easily find solutions when solving problems obtained the lowest mean rating of 2.54, $SD=0.885$ which is verbally interpreted to some extent. This implies that the students themselves also perceived that they can easily find solutions when solving problems to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

The SPC Education Ministry (2018) included in one of its Ten Performance Commitments for Basic Education Mathematics Program that a Paulinian learner must take the risk of trying out combinations of data, materials, methods, and techniques to derive and test potential solutions to existing problems even at the risk of criticisms. Upon formulating CONS outcomes and competencies indicators, it was understood by the researcher that in the aspect of the affective domain of learning, risk-taking is one of the components of becoming a self-directed and role model person and this value is affected by the level of attitude and anxiety one experience (Pa, 2013). As observed, students during their classes particularly during their Mathematics class are normally afraid of trying to answer board problems or afraid of even responding to the formative questions of the teacher because of their fear to be criticized by their classmates and because of the possible anxiety after being corrected and remarked by their teachers rather than gaining support from teachers and classmates to succeed with correct solutions to the posed problems. Alongside these ideas, Pantziara & Philippou (2015) made mention that students' affective domain has been popular in the mathematics education community in an ongoing attempt to understand students' learning behavior. Students' performance and their interest in mathematics were influenced by fear of failure, self-efficacy beliefs, and achievement goals. Additionally, the affective variables such as attitude, motivation, anxiety, beliefs, and values were strongly linked to the quality of teaching and learning mathematics. Unfortunately, these values seem to receive the least attention although it is one of the most stable affective domains. This is because most people viewed mathematics as value-free, where it has various values related to it (Pa, N. A. N., & Tapsir, R., 2013).

The results discussed are considerably consistent with the claim of Singh & Yu (2018) that what makes mathematics a commonly difficult subject to most of the learners is because of its problem solving, reasoning, and critical thinking aspects which most of the learners do not easily possess or develop. Mathematical knowledge learning and integration of the conceptual approaches in learning are difficult to achieve because of the subject's procedural approach. Khair & Khairani (2012) also stated that students suffering from difficulties in mathematics at all levels are noticeable. The students cannot easily come out with problem solutions because of related problems with reasoning and the ability to translate mathematical problems into solvable equations. Furthermore, most of the mathematics learners are bound to how the problems are solved in front of them as demonstrated by the teacher by which with lesser mastery, the students cannot cope up with the techniques of the teacher and so making them only bound to how the teachers solve the posed problems leaving them unable to find solutions or solving ways on their own.

In short, it can be inferred that for both teachers and students, the students under study are indeed likely to have difficulty in taking risks in finding solutions to problems and answer such problems in a given time duration when they do not feel it easy to find solutions when solving mathematical problems.

Considering all these findings shown in Table 1, it is now revealed that there is a significant difference between the teachers and students' perceptions on indicators 4 exhibit honesty ($p=0.004$) and 5. exhibit a sense of truthfulness ($p=0.018$) under the CONS mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study. However, looking into the rest of the indicators and the overall results, it can be inferred that there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of the CONS mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students ($p=0.083$).

Based on the preceding discussions, it was inferred that values integration and even spirituality promotion are not always the easiest to integrate with mathematical knowledge learning. Unfortunately, values seem to receive the least attention although it is one of the most stable affective domains. Thus, the teachers and students differently believed in the concepts of honesty

and truthfulness that are being intended for the students under study to embody. By the results in Table 1, the teachers believed that the students under study achieve to very much extent and the highest in these indicators under CONS category but for the students, they believed that these indicators are one of those which are achieved only to some extent and lower compared to other indicators under CONS category.

Observing significant differences between the teachers and students on the honesty and truthfulness behavioral traits may imply that mathematics teachers should deepen further, clarify, and transparently interject values integration across all topics under mathematics where honesty and truthfulness are consistently emphasized so that the learners will be able to fully embody these behaviors the way teachers and the topic outcomes expect the learners to exhibit.

Table2. The COM mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by the participants

Indicator s	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	p-value
17. Express compassion towards one another as students fulfill their tasks.	3.00	(0.632)	TSE	2.91	(.779)	TSE	0.806
18. Express empathy as students fulfill their tasks.	3.17	(.753)	TSE	2.93	(.770)	TSE	0.444
19. Exhibit generosity as students fulfill their tasks.	3.00	(.632)	TSE	3.03	(.828)	TSE	0.923
20. Take responsibility in thoughts and actions objectively.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.95	(.769)	TSE	0.502
21. Respect one's uniqueness and giftedness	3.83	(.408)	TVME	3.37	(.763)	TVME	0.143
22. Relate to all warmly and graciously without biases.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	3.09	(.819)	TSE	0.827
23. Demonstrate kindness or sensitivity to the needs and feelings of others.	3.50	(.548)	TVME	3.22	(.774)	TSE	0.380
24. Associate mathematical problems to certain scenarios that promote the Love of Christ.	3.00	(.000)	TSE	3.02	(.948)	TSE	0.959
25. Willingly share their time, resources, and energy for the accomplishment of a particular task.	3.17	(.753)	TSE	3.11	(.735)	TSE	0.860
Average	3.17	(.408)	TSE	3.0	(.672)	TSE	0.647

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

COM = Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value Independent samples t-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale:	Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
	3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
	1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
	1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Table 2 presents the COM mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves. For teachers, the COM was achieved by the students to some extent given the average Mean=3.17 and

average $SD=0.408$. Likewise, the student participants also perceived that they achieved COM to some extent given the average Mean=3.04 and average $SD=0.672$. This means that both teachers and students perceived that the students are compassionate, committed advocates for peace and universal well-being impelled by the Charity of Christ to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Moving forward, it can be seen that for teachers, indicator 5 respect one's uniqueness and giftedness obtained the highest mean rating of 3.83, $SD=0.408$, and verbally interpreted to very much extent. This is consistent with the students' perceptions where indicator 5 respect one's uniqueness and giftedness also obtained the highest mean rating of 3.37, $SD=0.763$, and verbally interpreted to very much extent. This implies that both teachers and students perceived that the students respect for one's uniqueness and giftedness to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

SPCEM (2018) states that a Paulinian who is expected to embody the "Compassionate, Committed Advocate for Peace and Universal Well-being" learning outcome which coexist with the Charity core value demonstrates one's compassion respecting dignity and equality of humankind and also actions that show one's care for all of God's creation and so inspire others to do the same. He or she commits oneself to be an advocate for universal well-being. He or she also relates with all warmly and graciously without biases and so takes time to listen or reach out to others.

Likewise, he or she must generally work hard to develop his or her God-given talents for the love of God in the service of the Church, family, and community and so becomes open to new inputs, suggestions and knows how to adjust performances and welcomes new learning in different situations.

Lastly, a Paulinian stands out for his or her uniqueness and originality and that he or she accomplishes tasks with determination, has good time management and self-discipline. Also, DepEd (2016) underscores the importance of implementing and greatly considering performance-based assessment to all Kto12 learners which point out that all educators are bound to measuring the actual outcomes and competencies performance or demonstration of learners which will then direct transfer of learning rather than just focusing on theoretical knowledge evaluation approaches.

Performance-based assessments enable the learners to unleash and exhibit their creativity, skillfulness, and abilities as they translate cognitive knowledge into tangible products, performance, or demonstrations of actually gained knowledge. Some of the school's commonly practiced performance assessments in relation to mathematics content are Math jingle, Lyrics composition, Role Play, Math race or trail, Math wizard and Quiz contest, Rubik's cube solving, Su Do Ku, and DaMath. For both teachers and students, fulfilling these tasks can also be a way to discover and display students' uniqueness and giftedness as they engage in the mathematics class.

Looking into the lowest mean results, it can be seen from Table 2 that indicators 17. express compassion towards one another as students fulfill their tasks (Mean=3.00, $SD=0.632$, and verbally interpreted To much extent), 19 exhibit generosity as students fulfill their tasks (Mean=3.00, $SD=0.632$, and verbally interpreted To much extent), and 24 associate mathematical problems to certain scenarios that promote the Love of Christ (Mean=3.00, $SD=0.000$, and verbally interpreted To some extent) obtained the lowest mean ratings compared to the other indicators under the COM category as to the teachers' responses. In relation to this, the students' perceptions column shows that indicator 17 express compassion towards one another as students fulfill their tasks (Mean=2.91, $SD=0.779$, and verbally interpreted To much extent) also obtained the lowest mean rating compared to the other indicators under COM.

SPCEM (2018) emphasized that a Paulinian demonstrates gestures that show kindness and sensitivity to the needs and feelings of others. Hence, the aforementioned outcomes and competencies indicators are rooted in these descriptions and statements and upon formulating these outcomes and competencies indicators, it is understood that expressing compassion,

exhibiting generosity, and consequently associating mathematical concepts promoting the Love of Christ are all interrelated fall under the affective domain of learning.

Moreover, the Department of Education (2016) emphasized that when the affective values are consistently integrated with the mathematics class and knowledge engagements as strongly promoted by the teachers' approaches and strategies, it is likely to yield a meaningful and valuable learning experience for Filipino learners that will last longer than the mathematical content knowledge itself. But as shown, it implies that both teachers and students have slight difficulty in terms of emphasis and promotion of compassion, generosity, and Love of Christ as they all engaged in the mathematics classes.

Hiebert & Grouws (2007) stated that traditionally, teachers focus on developing students' procedural skills rather than the cognitive and contextual aspects particularly in the area of Mathematics. The mathematics class is based on direct instruction where teachers review mathematical concepts, present the procedures required to solve tasks, and then have students practice these procedures with traditional problems. As observed by the researcher and by experience, values integration and even spirituality promotion are some of the hardest methods to interject and integrate with mathematical knowledge learning.

Considering all these findings shown in Table 2, it revealed that there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of the COM mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as to the individual indicators and also the average ($p=0.647$). Thus generally, the teachers and students perceived similarly as to the extent of the COM mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study.

The desired behaviors of a Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being are attainable and achievable through the implementation of SPCEM and DepEd Order No. 042 s.2016 prescribed teaching strategies and approaches. With all these strategies and approaches, it is believed by the researcher that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behaviors of compassionate, committed advocates for peace and universal well-being who are impelled by the Charity of Christ as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Table 3. The CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by the participants

Indicators	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	p-value
	26. creatively demonstrate resourcefulness upon fulfilling mathematical tasks.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.84	(.731)	TSE
27. exhibit giftedness as students translate mathematical knowledge into meaningful contexts.	3.00	(.000)	TSE	2.70	(.781)	TSE	0.353
28. relate prior knowledge to the new concepts and openly accept it as students apply knowledge in real-life experiences.	3.00	(.000)	TSE	2.91	(.827)	TSE	0.785
29. find an alternative or substitute for a learning material/activity to visualize a concept.	3.33	(.516)	TVM	2.99	(.770)	TSE	0.286
30. accomplish tasks with competence and determination.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.93	(.784)	TSE	0.459
31. exhibit craftsmanship in fulfilling tasks by being skillful, practical, and innovative.	3.00	(.000)	TSE	2.89	(.818)	TSE	0.752
32. show proficiency in understanding mathematical problems	2.83	(.408)	TSE	2.81	(.778)	TSE	0.953
33. explore patterns in finding solutions to problems.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.96	(.832)	TSE	0.547
34. illustrate ideas and make decisions when solving problems.	3.00	(.000)	TSE	2.95	(.815)	TSE	0.874
35. acknowledge points for improvement when solving problems	3.33	(.516)	TVM	3.01	(.796)	TSE	0.321

36. use imagination to solve problems.	3.00	(.632)	TSE	2.94	(.881)	TSE	0.870
37. simplify complex tasks by breaking it down into orderly manageable parts.	3.00	(.632)	TSE	2.86	(.783)	TSE	0.669
38. can exhibit proficiency in solving real-world problems using appropriate learning tools or resources	2.83	(.408)	TSE	2.81	(.761)	TSE	0.952
39. create options in facing and solving problems.	3.00	(.632)	TSE	2.88	(.832)	TSE	0.729
40. evaluate relevant and creative options in facing and solving problems.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.86	(.783)	TSE	0.344
41. define issues, problems, and opportunities to generate possible solutions to a problem.	2.83	(.408)	TSE	2.93	(.758)	TSE	0.764
42. evaluate students' solutions to problems whether such are best appropriate and applicable or not.	3.17	(.408)	TSE	2.99	(.774)	TSE	0.573
43. illustrate ideas and scenarios by translating mathematical knowledge from numerical statements into real-world contexts.	3.50	(.548)	TSE	2.91	(.819)	TSE	0.081
44. can construct new insights from their own experiences and realizations after solving mathematical problems.	3.17	(.753)	TSE	2.93	(.767)	TSE	0.454
Average	3.00	(.000)	TSE	2.93	(.618)	TSE	0.794

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

COM = Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value Independent samples t-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale:	Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
	3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
	1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
	1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Table 3 shows the CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves. For teachers, CRE was achieved by the students under study to some extent given the average Mean=3.00 and average SD=0.000. For the students, CRE was achieved by the students under study to some extent given the average Mean=2.93 and average SD=0.618. This means that both teachers and students perceived that the students are creative, resourceful explorers & problem solvers exhibiting the charism core value to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. Furthermore, Table 3 shows that for teachers, indicator 9 illustrate ideas and scenarios by translating mathematical knowledge from numerical statements into the real-world contexts obtained the highest mean rating of 3.50, SD=0.548, and verbally interpreted To very much extent. This implies that the teachers perceived that the under study illustrated ideas and scenarios by translating mathematical knowledge from numerical statements into real-world contexts to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. For the students, indicator 35. acknowledge points for improvement when solving problems obtained the highest mean rating of 3.01, SD=0.796, and verbally interpreted To some extent. This implies that the students believed that they acknowledge points for improving when solving problems to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. The teachers' and students' highest perception results may have differed but are related to each other. It can be understood that learners who can illustrate ideas and scenarios by translating mathematical knowledge from numerical statements into real-

world contexts may mean that they can also acknowledge points for improvement when solving problems since they can understand mathematical problems evident in their ability to translate mathematical knowledge.

The SPC Education Ministry (2018) included in one of its Ten Performance Commitments for Basic Education Mathematics Program that a Paulinian learner must search voluntarily beyond readily available resources of information, resources, and standard techniques to generate new understanding towards workable solutions to existing problems.

A Paulinian who is expected to embody the creative, resourceful explorer & problem solver learning outcome exhibiting the charism core value uses original ideas to create solutions to existing problems. In support to this, the Department of Education (2016) underscores the importance of transfer of learning principle by emphasizing that educators, the curriculum, and the content must always include and ascertain transfer of learning to sustain and apply knowledge in the real world or context and so provide meaningful learning for learners across all levels in all subjects by effective means of assessment (Cree & Macaulay, 2000). To ensure this, one of the basic and primary competencies the mathematics education framework intends to all Kto12 learners is that they must demonstrate the capacity and skill on illustrating mathematical problems and translating numerical statements into real-world problems and vice versa.

Additionally, the Kto12 Mathematics Education Framework of the Philippines also indicated in one of its competency standards that the learners must be able to demonstrate the skill of problem-solving, posing and solving his or her problem, and be able to validate and review his or her solutions whether such are accurate or otherwise (DepEd, 2016). Considering all these concepts our educators have considered in the implementation of the mathematics curriculum, it is indeed acceptable and likely that the students will highly acknowledge points for improvement when solving problems.

Looking closely to the lowest results under CRE category, indicators 32. show proficiency in understanding mathematical problems (Mean=2.83, SD=0.408, and verbally interpreted as To much extent), 38. can exhibit proficiency in solving real-world problems using appropriate learning tools or resources (Mean=2.83, SD=0.408, and verbally interpreted as To much extent), and 41. define issues, problems, and opportunities to generate possible solutions to a problem (Mean=2.83, SD=0.408, and verbally interpreted as To some extent) obtained the lowest mean ratings as to the teachers' perceptions. These all imply that the teachers perceived that the students under study have demonstrated these indicators to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes although adjudged as the lowest among the other outcomes and competencies.

For the students, indicator 27. exhibit giftedness as students translates mathematical knowledge into meaningful contexts obtained the lowest mean rating of 2.70, SD=0.781, and verbally interpreted To Some Extent. This implies that the students believed that they have exhibited giftedness as they translate mathematical knowledge into meaningful contexts to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Observing these indicators, it can be understood that they are related to each other since they all pertain to skills in solving mathematical problems. As underscored in the preceding discussions, what makes mathematics a commonly difficult subject to most of the learners is because of its problem solving, reasoning, and critical thinking aspects which most of the learners cannot easily possess or develop (Singh & Yu, 2018). Furthermore, most of the mathematics learners are limited only to how the problems are solved as demonstrated by the teacher who may not demonstrate ample mastery of the process for solving the problem. Consequently, the students cannot cope with the individual techniques of the teacher thus leaving them unable to find solutions or solving processes on their own. Khair & Khairani (2012) also stated that students suffering from difficulties in mathematics at all levels are noticeable. The students cannot easily come out with problem solutions because of related problems with reasoning and the ability to translate mathematical problems into solvable equations.

The term giftedness may refer to students having gifts and talents to perform or execute at higher levels compared to others of the same age, sex, experience, and environment in one or more domains (Steinmeyer, 2020). Also, intellectual giftedness is an intellectual ability significantly higher than average (Mackintosh, 2011). Focusing on the giftedness itself, a Paulinian student must generally work hard to develop his or her God-given talents for the love of God in the service of

the Church, family, and community. He or she also is open to new inputs, suggestions, and knows how to adjust performances and welcomes new learning in different situations. Moreover, a creative Paulinian stands out for his or her uniqueness and originality and that he or she accomplishes tasks with determination.

As advocates of Charism core value, he or she shares his or her talents and resources most especially to the most needed and that he or she inspires others to do their best, using his or her highest potential in any performances. In relation, a gifted Paulinian performs excellently in his or her studies, projects, and assigned tasks and further assists in the development and empowerment of others (SPCEM, 2018). For both teachers and students, fulfilling these tasks can also be a way to discover and display students' uniqueness and giftedness as they engaged in the mathematics class.

In the aspect of intellectual giftedness however where mathematical capabilities are given, Khair & Khairani (2012) stated that the learners commonly experience difficulties at all levels, resulting in some students' negative bias and sometimes expressed dislike for the subject.

Table 3 as well shows that there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of the CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as to the individual indicators and the average ($p=0.794$). Thus generally, the teachers and students perceived similarly as to the extent of the CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study.

The data also implies that the students have achieved the CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies as what their mathematics teachers anticipate. As SPC Education Ministry (2018) defined, a creative, resourceful explorer & problem solver Paulinian works hard to develop his or her God-given talents for the love of God in the service of the Church, family, and community. He or she also is open to new inputs, suggestions, and knows how to adjust performances and welcomes new learning in different situations. Moreover, a creative Paulinian stands out for his or her uniqueness and originality and that he or she accomplishes tasks with determination, has good time management and self-discipline.

A problem solver and critical thinker Paulinian makes the good and right decision in his or her choices and in solving problems. Being a critical thinker too, a Paulinian stands for the truth regardless of criticism or non-acceptance of others of him or her choices and in solving problems. Being a critical thinker too, a Paulinian stands for the truth regardless of criticism or non-acceptance of others of him or her. Furthermore, a resourceful explorer Paulinian uses original ideas to create solutions to existing problems. As advocates of Charism core value, he or she shares his or her talents and resources most especially to the most needed and that he or she inspires others to do their best, using his or her highest potential in any performances. In relation, a gifted Paulinian performs excellently in his or her studies, projects, and assigned tasks and further assists in the development and empowerment of others. Lastly, a creative and talented resourceful Paulinian shares openly and generously at the service of his or her class, family, Church, and Community every project and endeavor even in small or humble tasks.

Additionally, Department of Education's (2016) Mathematics Education Curriculum Framework in the Philippines provides a complete depiction of the end competency goals of the Department of Education for all learners under the Mathematics Curriculum— to yield citizens who are proficient in critical thinking and problem solving, through various surrounding efficient and higher-order strategies.

As said, the Kto12 Mathematics Twin Competency Goals are Critical Thinking and Problem Solving which are mostly contained in the CRE learning outcome and competency category or group.

Khair & Khairani (2012) stressed that there is an inevitable correlation between teaching efficiency and learning assurance in the mathematics subject. It is noticeable also that students are suffering from difficulties in mathematics at all levels. To improve the mathematics teaching and raise students' achievement level in mathematics is to rehabilitate the teacher of mathematics and provide him/her with educational training programs, upgrade his/her level academically and professionally through the educational supervision services. Schools and academicians should consider focusing on detecting mathematics teaching difficulties and examining the mathematics teaching strategies and methods of evaluation employed in teaching mathematics.

Table 4. COL mathematics learning outcomes and competencies as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students

Indicators	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test	
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	p-value	
1. show credibility as students fulfill their mathematical tasks.	3.17	.753	TSE	2.95	.759	TSE	0.475	
2. show accountability as students fulfill their mathematical tasks.	3.17	.753	TSE	2.95	.769	TSE	0.506	
3. demonstrate good interpersonal communications and teamwork during collaborative tasks.	3.33	.516	TVME	3.00	.783	TSE	0.304	
4. demonstrate leadership skills as students fulfill their mathematical tasks.	3.50	.548	TVME	2.67	.914	TSE	0.209	
5. recognize weaknesses, strengths, needs, and wants of fellow group members during learning activities.	3.17	.753	TSE	3.08	.779	TSE	0.788	
6. demonstrate a sense of pride when a task is completed successfully.	3.50	.548	TVME	2.95	.777	TSE	0.091	
7. observe conscientiously the guidelines needed in the accomplishment of tasks.	3.17	.408	TSE	3.09	.706	TSE	0.799	
8. exert effort to promote unity and collaboration in doing group tasks.	3.33	.516	TVME	3.17	.737	TSE	0.597	
9. act decisively as students choose the options when solving problems.	3.00	.632	TSE	2.94	.741	TSE	0.846	
	Average	3.50	.548	TVME	3.01	.605	TSE	0.051

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

COM = Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value Independent samples t-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale:	Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
	3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
	1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
	1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Table 4 presents the COL mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves.

Looking closely to the data presented, it can be gleaned that for teachers, COL was achieved by the students under study to very much extent given the average Mean=3.50 and average SD=0.548 which means that the teachers perceived that the students are collaborative, credible, responsive communicators & team players exhibiting the community core value to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. For the student participants, COL was achieved by the students under study to some extent given the average Mean=3.01 and average SD=0.605 which means that the students perceived that they are collaborative, credible, responsive communicators & team players exhibiting the community core value to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

As to the specific indicators, it can be inferred that for teachers, indicator 6 demonstrate a sense of pride when a task is completed successfully obtained the highest mean rating of 3.50, SD=0.548,

and verbally interpreted To very much extent. This implies that the teachers perceived that the students under study demonstrated a sense of pride when a task is completed successfully to very much extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. For the students, indicator 8 exert effort to promote unity and collaboration in doing group tasks obtained the highest mean rating of 3.17, $SD=0.737$, and verbally interpreted To some extent. This implies that the respondents believed that the students exert effort to promote unity and collaboration in doing group tasks to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Looking closely at the said indicator, it is perceived by the researcher that demonstrating a sense of pride and exerting effort to promote unity and collaboration are likely to be associated with learner's attitudes towards the mathematics subject.

Kishore (2014) stated that there is a significant positive relationship between attitudes towards mathematics and mathematics achievement. Ozer (2009) even mentioned that emotions such as confidence and esteem along with student background in mathematics and also learning strategies and school environment have significant effects on academic achievement. Hammouri (2004) emphasized also that learners and even their mothers' perception of success attribution to hard work, attitudes towards mathematics, and confidence in mathematics ability have strong positive total effects on mathematics achievement. Since mathematics is a difficult subject (Singh & Yu, 2018), it is indeed motivating and reinforcing to the learners when they can surpass and respond to problems and so generally achieve in mathematics.

A Paulinian student also demonstrates positive interpersonal relationships and sensibility to the feelings of others. He communicates and works well with others to resolve conflicts fairly. He must also develop and exercise the capacity for moral leadership that contributes to the welfare and for the common good of the family, classroom, school, and community. As responsive communicators, a Paulinian speaks prudently so as not to hurt others. Furthermore, as a credible and collaborative Paulinian, he or she exerts effort to promote unity and cooperation in the class, family, and community (SPCEM, 2018).

As to the lowest results under the COL category, indicator 9 act decisively as students choose the options when solving problems obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.00, $SD=0.632$, and verbally interpreted to some extent as to the teachers' perceptions. This implies that the teachers believed that the students under study act decisively as students choose the options when solving problems to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes. For the students, indicator 48, demonstrate leadership skills as students fulfill their mathematical tasks obtaining a mean of 2.67, $SD=0.914$, and verbally interpreted To some extent. This implies that for the students, they can demonstrate leadership skills to some extent as they engage in their mathematics classes. The learners may likely to have difficulty in demonstrating leadership skills and capabilities while fulfilling their mathematical tasks when they are experiencing difficulties with their peers and with the mathematics subject itself.

Paulinians who are collaborative, credible, responsive communicators & team players generally demonstrate habits that promote the success of the community and the skills needed to participate in the democratic process. He or she communicates and works well with others to resolve conflicts fairly (SPCEM, 2018). Boston (2017) also emphasized that in collaborative tasks, learners are trained to develop or enhance interpersonal relationships, unity, and harmony through effective communications while doing their group tasks which also allow learners to practice and display decision-making capabilities in selecting or making their problem solutions that will be beneficial for the team. Moreover, he also believes that implementing tasks that promote critical thinking for decision making, problem-solving, and conceptual understanding helps students see themselves as doers and sense makers of mathematics.

Normally, learners are led to always come up with solutions to solve problems by either allowing them to craft their procedures or choosing the best solutions from a variety of possibilities. Conversely, when the students are not properly knowledgeable of the problem solutions on the procedural and contextual approaches of the subject, they are likely to have difficulties in solving the same. Teaching and learning principles help educators achieve this outcome and competency. One is the Cooperative Learning principle which puts a premium on active learning achievable by letting learners work with fellow students as they all engage in a shared task (DepEd, 2016).

Table 4 finally shows that there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of the COL mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as to the individual indicators and also the average ($p=0.051$). Thus, generally, the teachers and students perceived similarly as to the extent of the COL mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Paulinians who are collaborative, credible, responsive communicators & team players are said to generally demonstrate habits that promote the success of the community and the skills needed to participate in the democratic process, demonstrate positive interpersonal relationships and sensibility to the feelings of others, communicate and work well with others to resolve conflicts fairly, observe the rules, policies, and regulations at home, Church, school, and community. Furthermore, they develop and exercise the capacity for moral leadership that contributes to the welfare and for the common good of the family, classroom, school, and community.

They offer assistance and support whenever needed and as responsive communicators, they speak prudently so as not to hurt others, exert effort to promote unity and cooperation in the class, family, and community. Also, they take pride in his or her Filipino identity and heritage and show a deep sense of community in social commitment, and for being collaborative and community loving, Paulinian work for the promotion of life, human rights, unity, justice, peace, and care of the environment (SPCEM, 2018).

The K to 12 Mathematics education framework in the Philippines which this study's conceptual framework is also based is supported by underlying learning principles and theories such as the Cooperative Learning which puts a premium on active learning achieved by working with fellow learners as they all engage in a shared task (DepEd, 2016). Discovery Learning and Inquiry-based Learning according to Bruner (1961) support the idea that students learn when they make use of personal experiences to discover facts, relationships, and concepts. With all these strategies and approaches, the researcher believes that it is certain that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behaviors of collaborative, credible, responsive communicators and team players who exhibit the Community core value as they engage in their mathematics classes.

Table 5. The CP mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by the participants

Indicators	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test p-value
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	
1. express conscience as students fulfill their commitment to our Paulinian mission.	3.3	.516	TVME	2.9	.74	TSE	0.212
	3			5	6		
2. express ethics as students fulfill their commitment to our Paulinian mission.	3.1	.753	TSE	2.9	.73	TSE	0.413
	7			1	9		
3. demonstrate productivity.	3.3	.516	TVME	2.9	.87	TSE	0.244
	3			1	1		
4. participate in activities and projects that promote Catholic formation, community service, and research.	3.3	.516	TVME	2.9	.83	TSE	0.266
	3			5	9		
5. demonstrate optimism in accomplishing tasks amidst difficulties.	3.1	.753	TSE	2.9	.76	TSE	0.454
	7			3	7		
6. show versatility in learning in order to attain greater outcomes.	3.3	.516	TVME	2.9	.72	TSE	0.228
	3			7	1		
7. independently share the Paulinian Mission and the Good News to all for the greater Glory of God.	3.1	.408	TSE	2.9	.80	TSE	0.52
	7			5	3		
8. willingly serve in every assigned task for the common good of everybody.	3.1	.408	TSE	2.9	.78	TSE	0.538
	7			7	7		
9. demonstrate critical thinking in solving mathematical problems.	2.8	.408	TSE	2.8	.74	TSE	0.842
	3			9	1		
10. demonstrate competence in understanding objectively	3.0	.000	TSE	2.9	.73	TSE	0.774
	0			1	0		

complex situations.

11. exhibit logical thinking in discerning solutions to mathematical problems.	3.0	.000	TSE	2.9	.71	TSE	0.982
	0			9	6		
12. consider mistakes as opportunities for self-improvement and learning.	3.3	.516	TVME	3.2	.78	TVME	0.898
	3			9	8		
Average	3.1	.408	TSE	3.0	.65	TSE	0.623
	7			3	7		

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

COM = Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value Independent samples t-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale:	Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
	3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
	1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
	1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Table 5 presents the CP mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves.

Looking closely at the data, it can be gleaned that for teachers, CP was achieved by the students under study to some extent given the average Mean=3.17 and average SD=0.408. Likewise, for the student participants, CP was achieved to some extent given the average Mean=3.03 and average SD=0.657. This means that for both teachers and students, the students are competent, conscientious, adept performers & achievers committed to one's mission in life to some extent as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

As to the specific indicators, indicators 54. express conscience as students fulfill their commitment to our Paulinian mission (Mean=3.33, SD= 0.516, verbally interpreted To very much extent), 3 demonstrate productivity (Mean=3.33, SD= 0.516, verbally interpreted To very much extent), 4 participate in activities and projects that promote Catholic formation, community service, and research (Mean=3.33, SD= 0.516, verbally interpreted To very much extent), 6 show versatility in learning in order to attain greater outcomes (Mean=3.33, SD= 0.516, verbally interpreted To very much extent), and 12 consider mistakes as opportunities for self-improvement and learning (Mean=3.33, SD= 0.516, verbally interpreted To very much extent) obtained the highest mean ratings under the CP mathematics learning outcomes and competencies as to the teachers' perceptions.

The result of students' responses also shows that indicator 65. consider mistakes as opportunities for self-improvement and learning (Mean=3.29, SD= 0.788, verbally interpreted To very much extent) obtained the highest mean rating under CP category.

A Paulinian who is a conscientious, adept performer & achiever committed to one's mission in life demonstrates initiatives to advance his or her skills and seeks an expert's opinion and credible facts and evidence. He or she continues doing work despite difficult situations and so he or she performs academic tasks the best way he or she can. An adept performing Paulinian stays focused on fully completing projects and tasks given. Being conscientious and committed to his or her mission, he or she proclaims Jesus Christ as the Good News to all and so gives his or her best in every assigned task for the greater glory of God. As a competent, adept performer and achiever, he or she also accepts suggestions and implements changes to improve one-self and takes mistakes as opportunities to change or improve himself or herself. Moreover, competent Paulinian works for excellence and initiates worthy projects up to completion for the common good always. He or she uses interpersonal and problem-solving skills to influence others. Being a conscientious achiever, he or she serves freely and generously without thought of reward or position. Finally, a conscientious, adept performer & achiever committed to one's mission in life

participates in all activities and projects of the class, family, Church, or community especially for the poor (SPCEM, 2018).

These desired behaviors are attainable and achievable through implementation of SPCEM and DepEd Order No. 042 s.2016 prescribed teaching strategies and approaches such as varying problem solving and creative thinking tasks plus a series of activities and instructional strategies that promote knowledge construction, decision making, and reasoning. Additionally, the Kto12 Mathematics education framework in the Philippines adopted by this study's conceptual framework is supported by underlying learning principles and theories such as the Constructivism approach which emphasizes that knowledge is constructed when the learner can draw ideas from his/her own experiences and connect them to new ideas (Steffe, 2012). With all these strategies and approaches, the researcher believes that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behavior of a conscientious, adept performer & achiever committed to one's mission in life as they engage in their mathematics classes.

On the other hand, indicator 9 demonstrate critical thinking in solving mathematical problems obtained the lowest mean rating (Mean=2.83, SD=0.408, and verbally interpreted To some extent) as to the teachers' perceptions. This data shows a similar outcome as to the students' perceptions showing that indicator 9 demonstrate critical thinking in solving mathematical problems obtained the lowest mean rating (Mean=2.95, SD=0.803, and verbally interpreted To some extent). Considering these consistent results, it implies that for both teachers and students, the students under study can demonstrate critical thinking in solving mathematical problems to some extent although the lowest among other indicators under the CP category as they engaged to their mathematics classes.

Critical thinking, according to Scriven and Paul (1987) is the intellectually disciplined process of actively and skillfully conceptualizing, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and/or evaluating information gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication, as a guide to belief and action. Moreover, there is a significant and positive relationship between attitudes towards mathematics and mathematics achievement (Ai, 2012; Ma & Kishore, 2014; Singh, Graville, & Dika, 2011).

DepEd (2016) stresses providing contextual learning in mathematics where educators should insert context in teaching mathematics. DepEd (2016) also defines context as a locale, situation, or set of conditions of Filipino learners that may influence their study and use of mathematics to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Contexts refer to beliefs, environment, language, and culture that include traditions and practices, as well as the learner's prior knowledge and experiences.

Considering all these findings, table 5 now reveals that there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of the CP mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as to the individual indicators and also the average ($p=0.623$). Thus generally, the teachers and students perceived similarly as to the extent of the CP mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as they engage in their mathematics classes.

The Kto12 Mathematics education framework in the Philippines which this study's conceptual framework is based is supported by underlying learning principles and theories such as Constructivism approach which emphasizes that knowledge is constructed when the learner can draw ideas from his/her own experiences and connect them to new ideas (Steffe, 2012). With all these strategies and approaches, the researcher believes that it will be certain that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behaviors of a conscientious, adept performer & achiever committed to one's mission in life as they engaged in their mathematics classes.

Table 6 shows the overall mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students under study as perceived by their mathematics teachers and the students themselves. It can be inferred from the data shown that for teachers, the overall mathematics learning outcomes and competencies were achieved by the students under study to some extent given the average Mean=3.23 and average SD=0.376. For the students, they also believed that they have achieved the overall mathematics learning outcomes and competencies to some extent given the average Mean=2.98 and average SD=0.638. The overall p-value is 0.440 implying that

there is no significant difference between the teachers' and students' perceptions on the extent of mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students.

Table 6. The overall mathematics learning outcomes and competencies achieved by the students as perceived by the participants

Learning Outcomes & Competencies	Teachers' Responses			Students' Responses			t-test
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	p-value
CONS (Conscious, Mindful Self-Directed Learners & RoleModels / Christ-centeredness Core Value)	3.33	(0.516)	TVME	2.8 7	(0.636)	TSE	0.083
COM (Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value)	3.17	(0.408)	TSE	3.0 4	(0.672)	TSE	0.647
CRE (Creative, Resourceful Explorer & Problem Solver /Charism Core Value)	3.00	(0.000)	TSE	2.9 3	(0.618)	TSE	0.794
COL (Collaborative, Credible, Responsive Communicators & Team Players / Community Core Value)	3.50	(0.548)	TVME	3.0 1	(0.605)	TSE	0.051
CP (Competent, Conscientious, Adept Performers & Achievers / Commission Core Value)	3.17	(0.408)	TSE	3.0 3	(0.657)	TSE	0.623
Average	3.23	(0.376)	TSE	2.9 8	(0.638)	TSE	0.440

Legend:

NEAA– No Extent At All, TLE– To Little Extent, TSE– To Some Extent, TVME– To Very Much Extent

COM = Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value Independent samples t-test significance: if $p < 0.05$

Ratings Scale: Mean	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Always	To Very Much Extent
2.51-3.25	Sometimes	To Some Extent
1.76-2.50	Rarely	To Little Extent
1.00-1.75	Never	No Extent At All

Furthermore, "Collaborative, Credible, Responsive Communicators & Team Players/Community Core Value" referred to as the COL category obtained the highest Mean among other categories according to the teachers' responses with $M=3.50$, $SD=0.548$ and verbally interpreted To Very Much Extent. This signified that the Mathematics teachers perceived that the students achieved COL to very much extent. Meanwhile, "Compassionate, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-being / Charity Core Value" referred to as the COM category had the highest Mean among other categories or groups under the students' responses column with 3.04 , $SD=0.672$ and verbally interpreted To Some Extent. This implies that the Junior High School students perceived that they achieved COM to some extent.

A Paulinian student demonstrates positive interpersonal relationships and sensibility to the feelings of others. He or she communicates and works well with others to resolve conflicts fairly. Moreover, Paulinians observe the rules, policies, and regulations at home, Church, school, and community.

He or she must also develop and exercise the capacity for moral leadership that contributes to the welfare and for the common good of the family, classroom, school, and community. As collaborative and team players, Paulinians also volunteer, offer assistance and support whenever needed. As a responsive communicator, a Paulinian speaks prudently so as not to hurt others. Furthermore, as a credible and collaborative Paulinian, he or she exerts effort to promote unity and cooperation in the class, family, and community. Also, he or she takes pride in his or her Filipino identity and heritage and shows a deep sense of community in social commitment. Lastly, a collaborative and community loving Paulinian works for the promotion of life, human rights, unity, justice, peace, and care of the environment (SPCEM, 2018).

These desired behaviors are attainable and achievable through implementation of SPCEM and DepEd Order No. 042 s.2016 prescribed teaching-learning strategies and approaches such as varying group collaborative tasks and series of activities and instructional strategies that promote interpersonal communications and reflective learning, love of culture and identity, leadership skills building, and care for others and the society. Additionally, the Kto12 Mathematics education framework in the Philippines which this study's conceptual framework is also based is supported by underlying learning principles and theories such as the Cooperative Learning which puts a premium on active learning achieved by working with fellow learners as they all engage in a shared task (DepEd, 2016). With all these strategies and approaches, the researcher believes that it is certain that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behaviors of collaborative, credible, responsive communicators and team players who exhibit the Community core value as they engage in their mathematics classes.

SPC Education Ministry (2018) also states that a Paulinian demonstrates gestures that show kindness and sensitivity to the needs and feelings of others. He or she plays fairly, answers exams and assignments, and does projects honestly. A compassionate Paulinian also shares time, resources, and energy to others willingly. Moreover, such Paulinian also respects the dignity and equality of all humankind. Being a humble peace advocate, a Paulinian also accepts defeat, gives forgiveness to those who hurt him or her, and celebrates others' success. Furthermore, he or she also relates with all warmly and graciously without biases and so takes time to listen or reach out to others. A compassionate and charitable Paulinian also shows warmth, love, and compassion, especially to the poor and suffering. He or she also cares for the environment and utilizes resources wisely and economically. Being a committed Paulinian, he or she behaves well everywhere and waits patiently for his or her turn. In relation to being committed advocate of universal well-being, a Paulinian takes care of God's creation and inspires others to do the same and so always commits oneself to be an advocate for peace and charity for all.

These desired behaviors are attainable and achievable through implementation of SPCEM and DepEd Order No. 042 s.2016 prescribed teaching strategies and approaches such as varying tasks and series of activities and instructional strategies that promote advocacy building and reflective & experiential learning, love of God, thy self & thy neighbor, and care for others and the society who are poor and sick in all aspects. Additionally, the Kto12 Mathematics education framework in the Philippines which this study's conceptual framework is based is supported by underlying learning principles and theories such as the Experiential & Situated Learning and Reflective Learning. As advocated by David Kolb (1984), experiential learning is the learning that occurs by making sense of direct everyday experiences. Experiential learning theory defines learning as "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming experience" (Kolb, 1984). Situated learning as theorized by Lave and Wenger (1984) is learning in the same context in which concepts and theories are applied and Reflective learning refers to learning that is facilitated by reflective thinking. It is not enough that learners encounter real-life situations. Deeper learning occurs when learners can think about their experiences and process these, allowing them the opportunity to make sense of and derive meaning from their experiences (DepEd, 2016). With all these strategies and approaches, it is believed by the researcher that Paulinians will demonstrate the appropriate behaviors of compassionate, committed advocates for peace and universal well-being who are impelled by the Charity of Christ as they engage in their mathematics classes. Looking closely to the lowest results, it can be inferred from Table 6 that for the teachers, the "Creative, Resourceful Explorer & Problem Solver/Charism Core Value" referred to as the CRE category obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.00, SD=0.000 and verbally interpreted To Some

Extent which implies that the Junior High School Paulinian Mathematics teachers perceived that CRE mathematics learning outcomes and competencies were achieved by their students only to some extent and the lowest among others. For the students, "Conscious, Mindful Self-Directed Learners & Role Models / Christ-centeredness Core Value" referred to as the CONS category had the lowest Mean as to the students' responses with 2.87, $SD=0.636$ and verbally interpreted To Some Ex- tent. This implies that the Junior High School students perceived that they achieved the CONS mathematics learning outcomes and competencies only to some extent and the lowest among others. Although these traits show the lowest results for teachers and students respectively, such traits still obtained an acceptable mean rating implying that the students were still able to achieve in these areas commendably.

Looking back to the features of the framework of Mathematics education in the Philippines as stated in the literature review and the preceding discussions, the said framework provides a complete depiction of the end competency goals of the Department of Education for all learners under the Mathematics Curriculum – to yield citizens who are proficient in critical thinking and problem solving, through various surrounding efficient and higher-order strategies (DepEd, 2016). Additionally, mathematics demands more on the mastery and deeper understanding of the subject leading to learners contextualize ideas relevant of values and holistic development, applying concepts to real-life situations, realizing and self-evaluating realistic mathematical knowledge absorbed, and creation of actual existence of Mathematical concepts in this world filled with lifechanging and affecting scenarios by which it requires each learner to transform or become critical thinkers and problem solvers who are upright and moral (Mastrangeli, 2019). Teachers normally focus on developing students' procedural skills rather than the cognitive and contextual aspects particularly in the area of Mathematics. The mathematics class is based on direct instruction where teachers review mathematical concepts, present the procedures required to solve tasks, and then have students practice these procedures with traditional problems (Hiebert & Grouws, 2007).

Values integration and even spirituality promotion are some of the hardest methods to interject and integrate with mathematical knowledge in all schools. Values integration and even spirituality promotion are not always the easiest to integrate with Mathematics. Values seem to receive the least attention although it is one of the most stable affective domains.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The students' achievements validate the teaching methodologies and approaches of the mathematics teachers relative to the subject outcomes and competencies.
2. The students' achieved mathematics learning outcomes and competencies match with the existing SPC Education Ministry Basic Education Level Outcome-based Education Framework which likewise contains the Life Performance Outcomes of the K-12 Paulinian learners.
3. The mark of Paulinian Education in St. Paul University Surigao Junior High School is its commitment and consistent implementation of Paulinian Spirituality and Holistic Excellence as emphasized by outcomes-based mathematics teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. That the findings of this study will be presented to the Junior High School students at the University. The essence and results of this study will give the students a glimpse of how they are achieving in the mathematics subject in a holistic approach. Moreover, the results of this study might also give them a generalized picture of the extent of their achievements in mathematics relative to their intended learning outcomes and subject competencies.
2. That the findings of this study will be presented to the Faculty of the University. This study would help the academic heads and teachers to revisit the present level of their teaching

capabilities matched with their content knowledge. Moreover, the results of this study may also allow the teachers to review their existing teaching capabilities side by side with the learners' intended content competencies, learning outcomes, and the learners' essential life elements to attain whether such are effective, aligned, and efficient.

3. That St. Paul University Surigao Academic heads or administrators consider the findings of this study in planning and crafting faculty training and development programs across all subject areas in the Basic Education Level focusing on the Outcomes-based Education Curriculum for Basic Education emphasizing marks of Paulinian Education in every subject area.

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